

Fracture Toughness of Structural SiCp-6061Al/6061Al Composite

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Summary: A structure-toughened SiC particle reinforced 6061 aluminum alloy matrix composite (SiCp-6061Al/6061Al) was designed and fabricated by vacuum infiltration processing. Its fracture toughness K_Q was tested by three-point bending method and compared with a conventionally stirring-cast SiCp/6061Al composite's in case of same particle size and volume fraction. The fractography of the SiCp-6061Al/6061Al composite was observed on a Cambridge Instrument S360 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The results showed that SiCp-6061Al/6061Al composite has a higher fracture toughness K_Q but a lower yield strength and a comparative elastic modulus. The crack opening displacement (COD) vs load curve of the designed composite showed that the fracture procedure of SiCp-6061Al/6061Al composite is by three stages and the maximum load on it can maintain for a long time. The deformation of the unreinforced 6061Al matrix and the SiCp-6061Al/6061Al interface debonding toughen this composite cooperatively. The complete fracture procedure of the designed composite was schemed by a model. This kind of composite can avoid abrupt failure occurring in most other conventional composite.

Keywords: 1 aluminum-matrix composites 2 fracture toughness 3 interface 4 structural

1. Introduction

Recently, silicon carbide Particle-reinforced Metal Matrix Composites (PMMCs) have been investigated numerously because of their high specific strength, specific elastic modulus, elevated temperature properties and low cost [1-4]. It has been shown that they are attractive for structural applications with non-extreme demand. However, the ductility and toughness of these materials are lower than that of their related matrix alloys due to the presence of brittle SiC particles [5-9]. This degradation in fracture critical properties has been one main obstacle to their applications for engineering.

According to some studies, the degradation in toughness of PMMCs has been mainly attributed to : 1) alteration in flow stress of matrix [10-12]. The addition of SiCp to metal can refine grain size of matrix and increase density of dislocation in matrix, thus makes flow stress in the matrix be more complicated than that in the unreinforced alloy [13]; 2) fracture of SiC particles. Large-sized SiC particles in PMMCs often fracture firstly because of its very low ductility (its strain to failure is less than 1%) or damage in the fabricated processing, and larger the particles size, larger the possibility of particle fracture [14-16]; 3) poor distribution of SiC particles [17]. The shear strain which develop in the matrix around the particles-agglomerated regions are larger than that around the uniformly-distributed regions (50%) [10]. So the micro-cracks will form in the particles-agglomerated regions and propagate along these regions preferentially; 4) decreases in tensile ductility. Although the addition of brittle SiCp increases the modulus and strength of matrix, it

also decreases the ductility of matrix simultaneously [17,18].

Analyses on fracture mechanisms of PMMCs have shown that fracture of most PMMCs is ductile but SiC particles localize the plastic deformation in the matrix seriously [9,19,20]. Arsenault et al [21] examined the dislocation density near the failure surface of a tensile sample. They found that the dislocation density was high near the fracture surface and decreased at a great rate as a function of distance from the fracture surface in a composite with a higher SiC content. Davidson [10] also noted that the maximum local strain near the fracture path is significantly in excess of the average strain to failure obtained by tensile tests. The nucleation positions of micro-voids are mainly fractured particles, localized matrices near particles or matrix / particle interface debonding [19,20]. However, the localized matrix among particles can not release the stress concentration around micro-voids and absorb fracture energy adequately. Therefore, the link and propagate between micro-voids is abrupt so that the fracture surfaces of PMMCs seem to be flat and there are tear ridges between particles rather than dimples [9,10,19]. So, it is regarded that there must be enough non-deformed plastic regions between reinforcements if one wants to toughen PMMCs. Recently Some laminate PMMCs have been studied to improve impact toughness based on this thought [22-24]. In the present study, a structurally toughening SiC particle reinforced 6061Al alloy composite (SiCp-6061Al/6061Al) was designed and fabricated based on the above thought. Its fracture model and mechanism was analyzed in detail.

2. Experimental materials and procedures

6061 aluminum alloy and 14 μ m nominal sized SiC particle are selected as the matrix and reinforcement. A vacuum infiltration processing is employed. The structure of the material SiCp-6061Al/6061Al after infiltrated is motioned in Figure 1. Simultaneously, a average 15% V_f SiCp/6061Al composite is fabricated by stirring casting method and casted as bar with diameter of 37.5 mm. The conditions of the two composites are listed in Table 1.

The two composites then are extruded as rods with diameter of 12mm by a 10:1 ratio at 400°C. The fracture toughness and crack growth behavior of these composites are evaluated using three-point bending sample with a single edge notch. 50 \times 10 \times 5mm rectangular samples are cut from these rods and notched with a root radius of 80 μ m. All samples are soluted at 520°C for 1 hour , then quenched in 20°C water followed by 8 hours of artificial aging at 160°C (T6). Three-point bending test is processed on a SCHENCK testing machine. Three samples are tested for each composite. To verify if the tested K_Q is valid K_{IC} , yield stress $\sigma_{0.2}$ and elastic modulus E of each composite also are measured. The bending fractographs of the two composites are observed on a Cambridge Instruments S360 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Optical Morphologies

Figure 2 shows the optical morphologies (OM) along the extruded direction (Fig. 2 a) and on the cross section (Fig.2b) of I composite and along the extruded direction of II composite (Fig.2 c).

3.2 Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the two composites are compared in Figure 3. All K_{IC} are not valid K_{IC} because width of the specimen (5mm) is smaller than $2.5(K_Q/\sigma_{0.2})^2$. Although K_Q of I is slightly higher than that of II, V_f of I (18%) is also higher than that of II (15%) and it is well known that fracture toughness of PMMCs decreases with increasing reinforcement V_f (3,25). So I composite is tougher than II. Their elastic modulus are approximately same but difference in the yield strength between the two composites is evident because yield of I begins in the unreinforced 6061Al matrix obviously (the yield strength of T6 treated 6061Al is about 280MPa (9)).

3.3 Analysis on fracture procedure

The crack opening displacement (COD) vs load curve of II (Fig. 4) shows II composite, like other most conventional PMMCs, fractures abruptly. The crack nucleation and growth are instantaneous (point D in Fig.4). Its fractography (Fig. 5 a) shows the crack mainly nucleates and propagates along the fracture particles and voids forming in the matrix near the interface.

However, the COD vs load curve of I (Fig. 4) shows another fracture model. The main crack forms on a slightly lower level of load, but grows on a higher level and propagates for a long displacement on the maximum load (at the end of the curve, the composite does not failure yet). That there are three curvatures (point A, B and C in Fig. 4) shows the failure procedure of I is by stages. Compared with its fractographs (Fig. 5 b), it can be seen that the main crack firstly forms in the first layer SiCp-6061Al bars (A-A section in Fig. 5 b) because the high V_f SiCp-6061Al bars are very brittle and will failure on a low level of strain (Fig. 5 c). When the crack rapidly grows to contact the ductile 6061Al, the matrix near the failure SiCp-6061Al bar begin to deform and absorb fracture energy. The crack then propagates along the interface perpendicular to the cross section. The load must increase to deform the matrix and make the crack propagate until the second layer bars failure (B-B section in Fig. 5 b). Similar procedure happens until the third layer bars failure (C-C section in Fig. 5 b). In Fig.5 d and e it can be seen that in fact the debonding of SiCp-6061Al/6061Al interface is the failure of SiCp-6061Al composite near the really interface. Therefore fracture SiCp-6061 bars still bear part of load to make crack propagate along longitudinal direction of them. After all bars failure, the maximum load still can maintain for long time until the 6061Al matrix failures. The complete fracture procedure can be illustrated by Fig.6. So, the ductile unreinforced 6061Al matrix between SiCp-6061Al bars and the SiCp-6061Al/6061Al interface debonding toughen this composite cooperatively and this kind of fracture model can protect the composite from disastrous failure occurring abruptly.

4. Conclusions

4.1 Controlled processing parameters well, a structure-designed toughening SiCp-6061Al/6061Al composite was fabricated successfully.

4.2 Compared with a conventional SiCp/6061Al composite, the designed composite has a higher fracture toughness but a lower yield strength and a same elastic modulus and shows a different fracture model.

4.3 The fracture procedure of the designed composite is by stages and the maximum load on it can maintain for a long time. This can avoid abrupt fracture occurring.

4.4 The deformation of the unreinforced 6061 matrix between SiCp-6061Al bars and the SiCp-6061Al/6061Al interface debonding toughen the designed composite cooperatively.

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Figure 1 Schematic diagram of SiCp-6061Al/6061Al composite after infiltrated

Figure 2 Optical morphologies of the two composites
 (a) cross section of I (b) along the extruded direction of I (c) along the extruded direction of II

Figure 3 Mechanical properties (K_Q , E , and $\sigma_{0.2}$) of the two composites

Figure 4 The COD vs load curves of the two composite

Figure 5 Fractographs of the two composite

(a) fracture of II composite (b) I composite fractures by stages (c) fracture of a SiCp-6061Al bar (d) and (e) the second crack propagates in the fracture bars

Figure 6 Schematic diagram of the complete fracture procedure of I composite
COD increases from (a) to (e)

Table 1 The conditions of the two composites

Materials	particle size (μm)	average particle V_f (%)	heat treatment	noted as
SiCp-6061Al/6061Al	14	18	T6	I
SiCp/6061Al	14	15	T6	II